

SCURVY VIII. FACTORS AFFECTING THE ANTI-SCORBUTIC VALUE OF FOODS¹

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NEW YORK

For many years following the classic exposition of Barlow and the studies to which it gave rise, scurvy aroused little interest and was represented in the literature merely by a succession of case reports. Of late, however, this subject has become one of the most active from the clinical as well as from the experimental standpoint. This striking change in the status of this disorder is due largely to the publications of Holst and his co-workers,² who opened the field to experimental study by demonstrating that scurvy can be induced readily in the guinea-pig. It has received additional impetus through the war, which unavoidably led to the development of scurvy, not only among the troops, but among the civilian population. As there has been no account of this chapter of the medical history of the war, it seems of interest to review briefly, even at this early date, some of the reports which are accessible, and which show that, in spite of our knowledge of prophylaxis, scurvy still must be regarded as one of war's vicissitudes.

In 1917 Harvier,³ a surgeon of the French army, was surprised to discover that 95 per cent. of the 800 troops of which he had charge suffered from scurvy; he tells us that other epidemic centers were

1. The previous articles of this series are:

1. Hess and Fish: Infantile Scurvy: The Blood, the Blood Vessels, and the Diet, *Am. J. Dis. Child* **8**:386, 1914.

2. Scurvy: A New Aspect of the Symptomatology, Pathology and Diet, *J. A. M. A.* **65**:1003, 1915.

3. Infantile Scurvy: Its Influence on Growth (Length and Weight), *Am. J. Dis. Child.* **12**:152, 1916.

4. The Therapeutic Value of Yeast and of Wheat Embryo, *Am. J. Dis. Child.* **13**:98, 1917.

5. Subacute and Latent Infantile Scurvy. The Cardiorespiratory Syndrome (A New Sign), *J. A. M. A.* **68**:235, 1917.

6. Infantile Scurvy: A Study of Its Pathogenesis, *Am. J. Dis. Child.* **14**:337, 1917.

7. The Rôle of Antiscorbutics in Our Dietary, *J. A. M. A.* **71**:941, 1918.

2. Holst, A., and Froelich, T.: *Ztschr. f. Hyg. u. Infektionskr.* **72**: 1912.

3. Harvier, P.: *Paris méd.* **7**:394, 1917.

recognized later outside this sector. Elsewhere we read⁴ of the occurrence of scurvy in France, involving 40 per cent. of 1,700 men of the South African Labor Corps and that this disorder was still more serious in another company owing to the fact that it was not recognized.⁵

Another author reports scurvy among the Italian troops,⁶ giving an account of an epidemic of some 200 cases of infectious purpura with manifestations of hemorrhagic scurvy. Still another reports that in June, 1916, scurvy broke out among some Italian troops which were stationed at an altitude of 1,500 to 2,000 meters.⁷ Vallardi gives an account of 180 cases among Italian troops in Macedonia, accompanied by slight jaundice and enlargement of the glands.⁸

It would seem that Germany likewise was not spared from this disorder, as is evidenced by a report of thirty cases noted by the French among prisoners of war captured in the beginning of 1917, which were once again diagnosed as purpuric rheumatism.⁹ Furthermore, Morowitz¹⁰ writes of scurvy in Germany among the soldiers, stating that it was confined mainly to the Eastern front. Both of these papers remark on the difficulty of differentiating scurvy from purpura. In this connection the statement of another German author¹¹ is interesting, namely, that during wars eruptions are apt to take on a hemorrhagic character; for example, in association with typhoid fever, cerebrospinal fever and rheumatism, and that this has been true in this war, in the Franco-Russian War of 1812 and in the Crimean War. He believes that, although scurvy has been prevented in this World's war, the latent type of the disease has not been eradicated. Another significant term is used by Blatt,¹² who writes of "a special department for scurvy containing about seventy patients."

It is of course not surprising to read of scurvy occurring in Russia. In the beginning of 1916, cases were reported among Russian prisoners,

4. Dyke, H. W.: *Lancet*, London **2**:513, 1918.

5. The writer adds that he believes that the health of the natives at home is protected by Kaffir beer which they consume even to the amount of 3 gallons a day, and which is made from germinated Kaffir corn. This cereal is germinated by steeping it in water for forty-eight hours and is then dried in the sun. Only enough is prepared for one brew. The French prepared a similar fermented beverage for these South African laborers, the sole difference in its mode of preparation being that the corn had not been germinated.

6. Vannutelli, F.: *Policlinico*, Rome **24**:873, 1917.

7. Gingui, F.: *Riforma med.* **34**:22, 1918.

8. Vallardi, C.: *Riforma med.* **34**:793, 1918.

9. Schreiber, G.: *Paris méd.* **26**:508, 1918.

10. Morowitz, P.: *München. med. Wchnschr.* **13**:349, 1918.

11. Von Niedner: *Med. Klin.* **14**:333, 1918.

12. Blatt, N.: *Wien. klin. Wchnschr.* **31**:942, 1918.

associated with the symptom of night-blindness.¹³ Elsewhere we read of 500 cases among prisoners captured in Turkestan.¹⁴

The data of the occurrence of scurvy among British troops is not yet available. There are many indications, however, which lead us to conclude that they also were affected. In one article 400 cases are referred to.¹⁵ This account likewise mentions night-blindness as a symptom, and notes the interesting fact that "scorbutic patients, when operated on, showed no particular tendency to hemorrhage." Most significant, however, are the preventive measures which were instituted by the British government. A body of 256 men, designated as the Madras Gardeners' Corps, were dispatched to Mesopotamia to plant gardens all over the country and to supply packets of seeds to various units.¹⁶ At Bagdad alone their output of vegetables was over 400,000 pounds. This is certainly a remarkable innovation in the hygiene of armies. Another significant point referred to in this article is that a new dietary scale, increasing the amount of vegetables, has been ordered for the British troops in India. The activity during the latter period of the war of the Lister Institute in investigating scurvy must also be interpreted as the response to an urgent demand for knowledge on this subject.

The civilian population was by no means spared. Indeed, it is probable that it suffered more widely in this regard. In Glasgow we learn of fifty cases developing in the Poor Law Hospital within a period of four months,¹⁷ and in Newcastle of sixteen cases appearing in the Poor Law Infirmary in the course of three months.¹⁸ A recent article from Vienna describes 200 cases occurring among older children, a situation quite unheard of in peace times.¹⁹ Morawitz¹⁰ also states that scurvy appeared mainly among civilians.

In its fully developed form scurvy must be considered an exceptional disorder in normal times. This applies to the United States and to most of Europe. In Russia and some other countries it is practically endemic. A recent communication from Aruba,²⁰ a small island of Dutch Guiana lying north of Venezuela, illustrates the fact that in some parts of the world scurvy is still a plague. This note tells of 3,000 cases of this disease occurring in 1915 among a population of less than 10,000, and adds that the crops have failed almost entirely during the years 1912, 1913 and 1914.

13. Zak, E.: *Wien. klin. Wchnschr.* **30**:592, 1917.

14. Disque: *Med. Klin.*, No. 1, 1918.

15. O'Shea, H. V.: *Practitioner*, London (October) **1**: 1918.

16. *Trop. Dis. Bull.* **12**:257, 1918.

17. Pickens, R. M.: *Lancet*, London **2**:21, 1917.

18. Harlan, G. P.: *Brit. M. J.* **2**:46, 1917.

19. Tobler, W.: *Ztschr. f. Kinderh.* **87**:459, 1918.

20. Hopkins, G. R.: *J. A. M. A.* **69**:1641, 1917.

It is difficult to estimate how common scurvy, and more especially infantile scurvy, is in the United States. A recent article by McLean²¹ gives an account of 50 cases admitted to the wards and outpatient department of the Babies' Hospital in New York City during a period of twenty months. Statistics, however, do not and cannot give an adequate idea of the incidence of nutritional disorders which require many months to develop fully. When we reflect that it usually requires about six months before a case of scurvy reaches the phase where it can be recognized clinically, it is clear that *the great majority of cases must be latent or rudimentary, and inaccessible to diagnosis by clinical or laboratory methods.* It would seem logical to believe that there is a considerable number of infants who for a period of one or more months are unwittingly deprived of the necessary quota of anti-scorbutic food, but who are saved from the manifest development of the disorder by a casual and fortunate change in their dietary.

MILK

The most important foodstuff in connection with scurvy in infants is the essential dietary of all babies, namely, milk. If milk were highly antiscorbutic, infantile scurvy would be a most exceptional disease. As brought out elsewhere, however, "raw milk must not be considered as having potent antiscorbutic properties."²¹ This was noted many years ago by Barlow²² in one of his later papers, and has been convincingly demonstrated by the recent experimental work of Chick and Hume²³ carried out in the Lister Institute. In numerous communications published during the past few years, we have laid emphasis on the fact that pasteurized milk possesses still less antiscorbutic power than raw milk; that, indeed, it is not sufficiently rich in this "vitamin"²⁴ to allow a positive balance to be maintained, so that infants fed for a considerable period on pasteurized milk develop a mild type of scurvy.

21. McLean, S.: Arch. Pediat. **35**:477, 1918.

22. Barlow, T.: Lancet, London **2**:1075, 1894.

23. Chick, H., and Hume, E.: Biochem. J. **12**:131, 1918.

24. There has been considerable discussion as to the proper generic term for the substances which are active in preventing scurvy, beriberi and other deficiency diseases. Some have preferred to use the indefinite term "accessory factor" rather than the word "vitamin," which connotes a definite chemical substance. "Accessory factor," however, leads one to infer that such a substance is not essential to well-being or to life in comparison to other food substances. In point of fact, just the opposite is true. We can prosper without fats or carbohydrates in our diet, but we cannot maintain health if the antiscorbutic factor, the antiberiberi factor, etc., are excluded from the dietary. From this point of view these substances are essentials for life, whereas the fats and the carbohydrates may be regarded individually as more truly "accessory."

We wish to point out again that this deficiency of pasteurized milk is due only in part to its having been heated, that much of the antiscorbutic factor is lost subsequent to the heating in the course of the handling and aging of the milk, so that pasteurized milk contains considerably less of the vitamin factor after forty-eight hours than it did immediately subsequent to heating. This is due in part to the fact that a large proportion of the acid-forming bacteria are killed, so that the milk gradually becomes less acid, developing a reaction which favors the loss of the antiscorbutic "vitamin." It is probably exceptional, however, for a well marked case of scurvy to develop on a diet of pasteurized milk, for enough of the protective substance remains to avert this disaster. In referring to scurvy occurring on this diet, we refer to the latent type of the disorder, characterized by stationary weight, fretfulness, a peculiar muddy complexion, rapidity of pulse and respiration (the cardiorespiratory syndrome) and slight edema over the tibiae; in some cases this condition advances further, merging into what may be termed subacute scurvy — where tenderness of the bones, scattered petechiae, and perhaps a fine hemorrhagic rim along the gums of the incisor teeth are added to complete the picture.

The more milk, whether raw or pasteurized, a baby receives, the less will be the chance of scurvy developing. This is likewise true in regard to experimental scurvy. It would seem that this fact constitutes conclusive evidence that this disorder is not brought about by an exogenous toxin existing in the milk, and also that it can be explained only on the supposition that a deficiency plays a rôle in the etiology of the disease. In considering whether a certain diet leads to scurvy, it is, therefore, of prime importance to know how much milk has been given. In most of communications, however, for example in the excellent report brought out some years ago by the American Pediatric Society, this item is not included in the data, so that it is impossible to appraise the rôle which the boiling or the pasteurization of the milk, or the addition of various proprietary foods, played in bringing about the disorder. Frequently many factors must be taken into consideration when analyzing the relation of a particular food to scurvy. For example, when we regard malt soup from this point of view (a preparation consisting of 1 pint of milk, 1 pint of water, with the addition of flour, malt and a small amount of potassium carbonate), a diet which in our experience induces scurvy most readily, we find that there are the following determinants leading to this result: the amount of milk is insufficient to fully protect; the preparation is boiled and frequently prepared originally from pasteurized milk; there is a period of aging between the pasteurization

and the boiling of the milk and the flour;²⁵ an alkali is added, thus hastening the decomposition of the "vitamin"; and finally, the additions to the milk may exert a detrimental influence. Some time ago, in making up malt soup preparations, raw milk was used for a certain number of infants and pasteurized milk for others. A distinct superiority was found in favor of the former as regards the development of latent scurvy, so that we would recommend that raw milk should be employed in preparing malt soup and similar formulas which involve heating.

Another milk formula which frequently leads to mild scurvy is Schloss milk, which contains 280 c.c. of milk and cream to the quart, in addition to sugar, flour, casein and potassium chlorate. Here again the small amount of milk is largely accountable for the production of scurvy, although there is probably the additional factor of low acidity, as it is only half as acid as raw milk, when measured by its power to neutralize a solution of sodium hydroxid. Reducing the acidity of a food does not entail an immediate loss of antiscorbutic vitamin, although it initiates a gradual and continuous loss of this substance. Just as we must consider exactly the nature of the diet, and more particularly the amount and quality of the milk in judging of the relation of a diet to scurvy, so in drawing conclusions as to the value of an antiscorbutic substance, the complete dietary must likewise be taken into account. It is evident, for example, that it will require less orange juice to cure a case of scurvy which has developed on a formula containing 24 ounces of pasteurized milk than one which has developed on a diet of malt soup. This point is rarely borne in mind. It is important to maintain the same viewpoint in judging those cases scattered through the literature where scurvy is reported to have developed in nursing babies. Probably one of the causative factors in these cases has been a deficiency in the amount of milk; in others, the hemorrhages associated with infection have been mistaken for scurvy.²⁶ There

25. Heating destroys to a greater or less degree the antiscorbutic "vitamin," so that if milk is pasteurized and also boiled, there is a double loss of this substance. However, this loss is greater if an interval is allowed to elapse following the pasteurization, for then the milk is also subjected to the deteriorating influence of age, which is considerable after prolonged heating at a low temperature.

26. There seems to be some misconception as to the pathogenesis of the subperiosteal hemorrhage in scurvy. In most reports this lesion is described as if it resulted from a hemorrhage burrowing its way beneath the periosteum and raising it from the subjacent bone. In point of fact, such an event is impossible, as will be fully realized when one experiences the great difficulty in separating periosteum from normal bone. Scurvy involves the periosteum which is not normal; it is insecurely attached to the shaft of the bone, so that it is readily stripped off by hemorrhage.

are a few reported cases, a very few, however, which are difficult to explain in these ways.

DRIED MILK

In view of the increasing use which is being made of dried milk, it seemed distinctly worth while to determine whether milk necessarily loses its antiscorbutic power in the course of drying. In their work on animal scurvy, Chick and Hume²⁷ employed dried milk as a part of their routine diet, as providing a well balanced ration which was devoid of the antiscorbutic factor. The milk which they used had been heated to 120 C. for an hour. It would be a mistake to infer from these experiments that all dried milk must be regarded as inert in this particular, for milk may be desiccated at a lower temperature, and one sustained for a much shorter period. We have tested a brand of dried milk which has been heated to about 116 C. for about one minute, and found that when it was given to the guinea-pig to the equivalent of 80 c.c. of fresh milk, it was able to cure scurvy. These experiments will be reported in detail elsewhere in connection with guinea-pig scurvy. We have had an opportunity, however, of testing this milk in two cases of human scurvy. The babies showed the typical signs of scurvy—peridental hemorrhage, tenderness of the femora, and the milder symptoms which we have heretofore enumerated. When the diet of the one child was changed from malt soup to 4 ounces of dried milk diluted with a quart of water, there occurred distinct improvement in all the scorbutic signs and in the general condition. In the other case the malt soup was replaced by the same quantity of dried milk solution (1 quart), to which, however, malt, flour and potassium chlorate were added according to the previous formula. In this instance likewise a decided improvement in the scorbutic signs occurred—the hemorrhages of the gums disappeared, the child soon began to stand, and her temperament became happier. It may seem that this result runs contrary to all that we know of the antiscorbutic “vitamin” and its sensitiveness to destruction by heat. We must remember, however, that there are many factors which determine whether or not heat shall bring about destruction of “vitamin.” For example, it was found that orange juice can be boiled for a period of at least ten minutes and lose very little of its antiscorbutic value.¹ Recently Harden, Zilva and Still²⁸ have shown that lemon juice may be reduced almost to the dry state and still retain its power. This resistance has been attributed to its acid reaction. We know, however, that cabbage may be dried and still retain

27. Chick, H., and Hume, E.: *Tr. Soc. Trop. Med. and Hyg.* **10**:141, 1917.

28. Harden, A.; Zilva, S., and Still, G. F.: *Lancet London* **1**:17, 1919.

a large amount of its antiscorbutic quality; this has been demonstrated by Holst²⁹ and recently proved by Givens and Cohen.³⁰ In this instance the acid reaction cannot be regarded as the protective influence. In the case of this dried milk we must bear in mind that it possessed a comparatively high degree of antiscorbutic power at the time of drying, which was carried out within six hours of the milking. Shortness of subjection to heat and rapidity of desiccation occasion a minimum degree of destruction. In connection with the effect of aging, of alkalization, of heating and probably of other agencies deleterious to this "vitamin," the length of time to which it is subjected to the injurious environment is in general more important than the intensity of the process.

The recent pronouncement of the Food (War) Committee of the Royal Society³¹ that the scurvy "vitamin is deficient in all dried and preserved foods" is evidently too sweeping. We shall see later that this criticism applies also in regard to a preserved food.

The fact that dried milk may largely retain its antiscorbutic value is of interest as indicating how little the milk has been changed from a biologic point of view, and therefore is important from a dietetic standpoint. It should be remembered, however, that milk heated for a long period in the course of drying loses much or all of its protective value, and furthermore, that our experience has not embraced the question of whether dried milk undergoes gradual changes in the course of a period of many months.

Babies fed on pasteurized milk must have additional antiscorbutic food in their dietary. This does not mean that human milk contains more of the antiscorbutic "vitamin" than does cow's milk, but merely that the attending circumstances render the latter less valuable in this regard. The fact that cow's milk is pasteurized or boiled, that it is not perfectly fresh and has undergone considerable handling, that it is diluted and cannot be given in full strength, all contribute to decrease its antiscorbutic potency.³²

29. Holst, A., and Froelich, T.: *Norsk. Mag. f. Laegevidensk.* **8**:989, 1916.

30. Givens, M. H., and Cohen, B.: *J. Biol. Chem.* **36**:127, 1918.

31. Food Committee, Royal Society: *Lancet*, London **2**:756, 1918.

32. It is not possible to say exactly how much raw milk a baby needs to protect it against the development of scurvy. We may, however, reach an approximate estimation of this figure. We know that it takes about 2 c.c. of orange juice to protect a guinea-pig against manifest scurvy, and about 10 c.c. to protect a baby. The ratio, therefore, between the guinea-pig and the infant in this regard would seem to be about 5 to 1. We also know that it takes about 80 to 100 c.c. daily of fresh cow's milk to protect a guinea-pig for long periods. If we assume the ratio of 5 to 1, it would therefore seem that it would require about 500 c.c., or a pint, of fresh raw milk daily as a minimum to protect the baby. (It is quite possible that a slight negative balance of the vitamin may exist unless a still greater amount is given.)

This raises the question as to just when the antiscorbutic diet should be introduced; at what age it should be added to the dietary of the bottle-fed infants. In point of fact this question is asking merely in an indirect way how long it is wise to allow a negative balance of scurvy "vitamin" to persist. Stated in this form it would seem that the answer must be that this deficiency should be allowed for as short a time as possible. In our experience there is no contra-indication whatever to giving a baby orange juice (or canned tomato) when it is a few weeks of age.

FRUITS

Orange juice must be regarded as the prototype of antiscorbutics. As far as we know, it shares with lemon juice the distinction of being the most potent food in this respect. It would be of no avail, in the present state of our knowledge, to consider in detail the nature and basis of this potency. There are some results, however, brought out by recent investigations which should be borne in mind. It has been shown that orange juice preserves its peculiar efficacy after it has been subjected to boiling for a period of ten minutes; that the active factor may be extracted by means of alcohol;³³ that it is not destroyed even though the juice be evaporated almost to dryness, and finally, that the orange juice seems to have lost none or little of its efficacy after it has been deprived of the free citric acid and other acids.³⁴ Recently it has been stated by McCollum and Pitz³⁵ that the antiscorbutic power of orange juice resides in its salt constituents; that a solution containing these salts in a proportion similar to that in the natural juice will possess the same therapeutic quality. In a previous article we have shown this not to have been our experience in the scurvy of guinea-pigs,³³ and have referred elsewhere to the fact that a preparation of this kind failed to cure the scurvy of infants. In one case (baby Margolis) 1 ounce of this "artificial orange juice" was given for a period of eighteen days. This baby had a pulse ranging from 164 to 196. The addition of this solution to the dietary did not increase the appetite or alleviate the symptoms in any way, nor did it act as a laxative. The sole effect which was observed was a diuretic action. In another case, which will be referred to later in connection with intravenous therapy, this treatment in the same dosage was continued for ten days and was then discontinued, as there was no beneficial result. We feel, therefore, that the value of orange juice

33. Hess, A. F., and Unger L.: *J. Biol. Chem.* **35**:487, 1918.

34. Harden, A., and Zilva, S.: *Biochem. J.* **12**:259, 1918.

35. McCollum, E. V., and Pitz, W.: *J. Biol. Chem.* **31**:229, 1917.

and similar antiscorbutic substances must be looked for elsewhere than in their salt constituents. Nor is their potency essentially united with their acid reaction, for orange juice may be alkaline and yet lose little or none of its activity. For example, the following case (Chart 1):

Chart 1.—Showing the cure of scurvy by means of orange juice which had been boiled and rendered alkaline previous to feeding.

Baby Kipnes, a poorly nourished baby having exudative diathesis and spasmophilia, weighed $15\frac{1}{4}$ pounds at 18 months. This baby developed subacute scurvy on a diet of malt soup which was made from raw milk. It evinced tenderness of the thighs, had the characteristic color and slight hemorrhages of the gums. From June 1 to July 10 it was given one tablespoonful of orange juice, which had been boiled and then made slightly alkaline to phenolphthalein by the addition of normal sodium hydroxid. The appetite improved rapidly, the occasional vomiting stopped and this improvement continued in spite of a mild febrile condition. When, on July 10, the raw acid orange juice was substituted, peculiarly enough the appetite lessened and there was a cessation of gain in weight (which, however, is not a reliable criterion of the value of an antiscorbutic).

Baby Hamburger, pale, had poor appetite, petechiae of the tongue and gums, and lack of gain in weight. From June 10 to July 3, a period of about three weeks, a small amount of lemon juice, one teaspoonful, was added to the dietary. The appetite remained poor, however. The dosage of the lemon juice was then increased to 2 teaspoonfuls daily for the succeeding five weeks. The baby gained and looked better. The juice was now rendered slightly alkaline, and given for the next two and one-half months in this form in the dose of 1 tablespoonful daily. The baby continued to prosper and to be entirely free from all signs of scurvy.

The neutralization of orange juice possesses some dietetic value. At times very young babies, generally those under 1 month of age, regurgitate orange juice. It has been found that if the juice is rendered neutral this difficulty is overcome. The rendering of the juice neutral offers no practical inconvenience, as it undergoes a decided color change as soon as it has become neutral or very slightly alkaline, assuming a more translucent and far deeper yel-

low or amber color. This change may be utilized by the nurses in determining the reaction, thus rendering titration or other time consuming methods unnecessary.

In three instances we have given boiled and neutralized, or slightly alkalized orange juice intravenously. Theoretically, there seemed no basis whatever for fearing that therapy of this kind could do any harm. The preparation is sterile, of neutral reaction, and contains sucrose and a number of salts which are present in the blood or in the organs of the body. We began with small injections, increasing them gradually, and learned very soon that the fluid was entirely innocuous. In no case was the slightest reaction noted either in the temperature or in the general condition of the child. This method was employed because it seemed that in this way a more rapid cure of the disorder might be effected than where absorption took place from the intestinal canal, and because, from a pathogenetic point of view, it would be of decided interest to determine whether or not scurvy could be cured by an extra-alimentary route. As far as we know, an endeavor of this kind has never been attempted. The first case in which use was made of this therapeutic method was that of the child (Margolis) on which "artificial orange juice" had been employed without success. After this failure mineral oil (albolene) was given for a week, nine teaspoonfuls a day. This, however, also proved of no avail. We then resorted to intravenous therapy. The orange juice was obtained in as sterile a manner as possible, boiled for about five minutes, and just previous to its injection was rendered neutral or slightly alkaline by the addition of normal sodium hydroxid. At first only a few cubic centimeters were injected. Gradually in this case and in others the dosage was increased so that as much as 30 c.c. were used at one time. In this case six injections were carried out during the period from April 29 to May 10, a total of 98 c.c. being given; that is, an average of 6.5 c.c. a day. The child showed no untoward reaction, but made decided improvement. An intercurrent infection, however, rendered it difficult to judge accurately as to the success of the treatment.

The second case in this series was another infant (Teitelbaum) to which "artificial orange juice" had brought about no beneficial result. This baby was 15 months old and had been fed for a long period on malt soup and cereal, having also received for many months 1 teaspoonful of cod liver oil three times a day. It had subacute scurvy, characterized by tenderness of the legs, hemorrhage of the gums and minor manifestations. Intravenous injections were carried out on May 1, 3, 5, 6, 8, 10, 13 and 17—87.5 c.c. being given in all. After the second injection, when 17.5 c.c. had been given,

marked improvement was noted; the gums were no longer hemorrhagic. There was diuresis accompanied by loss of weight. This loss was merely temporary and by the ninth of the month a gain set in which continued.

The third case is the most interesting and will be given in somewhat greater detail. This child (Sheratzky) was 16 months old and had hemorrhage of the gums and tenderness of the leg, which was held in the characteristic flexed and averted position. Five tests carried out on nonsuccessive days showed a daily excretion of urine of 350, 400, 200, 150 and 300 c.c. Phenolsulphonephthalein tests showed an output in the course of two hours of from 50 to 70 per cent. No casts or red blood cells were found in the urine. There was moderate anemia, 3,150,000 red cells, 70 per cent. hemoglobin, 20,000 leukocytes, of which 75 per cent. were polynuclears. The carbon dioxid tension of the lungs was 30. The chemical tests of the blood gave the following results: Urea nitrogen, 12.6; carbon-dioxid tension, 68; sugar, 0.12, and diastatic activity, 11.0. These tests were performed by Dr. John Killian and will be reported elsewhere in a paper on the chemistry of the blood in scurvy.

It seemed that this would be an excellent case in which to try the benefit of eliminative treatment. Accordingly, 6 grains a day of Dover's powder were given, an increased amount of water ordered, and the child was placed in a warm room to promote perspiration. A few days later caffeine, $1\frac{1}{2}$ grains, was injected hypodermically every four hours to promote diuresis, and 2 tablespoonfuls of liquid petrolatum three times a day, to increase elimination from the bowels. As there was no noticeable improvement from this treatment it seemed of advantage to attempt a cure by means of flushing out the blood stream. Accordingly, 250 c.c. of physiologic sodium chlorid solution were given intravenously and repeated on the following day. It would seem that if eliminative treatment can be successful it should be accomplished by this method. As an illustration of the extent of elimination brought about by this procedure, the following figures are of interest. At 2 p. m., when the infusion was begun, the baby weighed 15.7 pounds; at 4:05, 15.8 pounds; at 4:45, 16 pounds; the next morning it had reverted to its original weight of 15.7 pounds. In other words, all the fluid injected had been eliminated. A similar result was brought about by the succeeding injection. Throughout this period the child not only passed plenty of urine, but perspired freely and had two or three loose stools a day. The symptoms, however, grew worse rather than better, so the eliminative treatment was discontinued and intravenous injections of orange juice were resorted to. At this time, in addition to the well-known signs

of scurvy, the baby showed a positive "capillary resistance test" (that is to say, it developed petechial spots on the forearm when a tourniquet was applied for three minutes to the upper arm). Four intravenous injections were given—6 c.c., 12 c.c., 6 c.c. and 36 c.c. Improvement was noted sixteen hours after the first injection and continued day by day. In six days the child had gained 10 ounces, was less irritable and the gums were much improved. On the eighth day following the first injection it was noted that the "capillary resistance test" had become negative; how soon this change took place was not recorded. From this time on the course was uneventful. It may be added that a test of the blood of this infant showed a calcium deficiency, which, as will be shown elsewhere, occurs very frequently in this disorder.

As mentioned, these cases received not only the intravenous therapy, but what may be termed eliminative treatment. Diuresis, catharsis and sweating were stimulated with the object of bringing about the excretion of possible toxin, and thus effecting a cure. In a recent article Gerstenberger³⁶ has laid emphasis on the diminution of the quantity of urine in the course of infantile scurvy, and in our preceding article we also brought out this point. In the foregoing cases our protocols show that the daily output of urine was increased by the citric acid in the "artificial orange juice," and was still further augmented by the intravenous injections of salt solution. The latter method should be of decided value in ridding the body of a toxin. In spite of a copious flushing of the blood, of the kidneys and of other organs, it did not, however, prove of value.

At the same time catharsis was brought about by means of ample doses of mineral oil (albolene). In several articles on scurvy in guinea-pigs we have shown that this disease is not due to impaction of feces, as McCollum and Pitz have suggested, and cannot be cured by means of cathartics.³⁷ These results have been obtained also by Rappleye³⁸ and by Cohen and Mendel.³⁹ A similar failure resulted where the mineral oil was given to babies. In the one instance (Margolis) 3 teaspoonfuls were given daily for about three weeks, and in the other for almost the same length of time. In neither case, although the bowels moved several times a day, was there the slightest improvement. Internal antiseptics were also tried, having in mind the claim that sodium benzoate is able to effect a cure in guinea-pig scurvy. *A priori* this treatment did not seem to offer great promise,

36. Gerstenberger, H. J.: *Am. J. Med. Sc.* **155**:253, 1918.

37. Hess, A. F., and Unger, A. F.: *Proc. Soc. Exper. Biol. and Med.* **15**:82, 1918.

38. Rappleye, W. C.: *Boston M. & S. J.* **179**:98, 1918.

39. Cohen, B., and Mendel, L. B.: *J. Biol. Chem.*, **35**:425, 1918.

in view of the fact that so many cases of scurvy, both in adults and in infants, have been mistakenly diagnosed as rheumatism and treated without avail with large doses of sodium salicylate. Moreover, when scurvy was so prevalent on board merchant ships, the sailors were given calomel and other mercurials in immense doses and it was found that these drugs did harm rather than good. On two occasions we gave 3 or 4 grains of sodium benzoate for a period of about ten days. It is hardly necessary to give the details of these cases; the results may be summarized by the statement that no improvement was noted following this medication. We may add that one of these patients had particularly foul stools. After the failure of sodium benzoate, 1 ounce of beef juice was given daily, which, as the result of its high protein content, rendered the stool still more foul. Nevertheless, the disorder improved on the beef juice. It may be added that even after this child was completely well its stools were exceptionally foul. From these various results, both in animals and in man, we conclude that intestinal putrefaction is not at the basis of scurvy, but that the primary disturbance is a food deficiency.

In the course of some years we have tried some fruits other than the orange, notably the banana, as it is available throughout the year and is being used more largely all the time. In one case banana was given for three weeks without definite improvement, although one half of a ripe banana was fed daily to a baby 15 months of age. In another case, in which this fruit was used for almost the same length of time, only slight improvement was noted. We believe, therefore, that banana possesses but mild antiscorbutic virtue. Following the failure of treatment with banana, potato was given, in order to note comparison between two foodstuffs which are chemically very similar. Both have a high magnesium relative to their calcium content, an alkaline ash and great caloric value.⁴⁰ Only one tablespoonful of potato was given daily, but there could be no doubt that even in this amount it was superior to the banana. The banana is deficient not only in antiscorbutic "vitamin" compared to other fruits, but according to recent investigation it contains very little water soluble "vitamin."⁴¹

Before closing the consideration of fruits we wish to record two experiences with the use of prune juice as a curative for scurvy. Although this food did not offer great promise, it seemed worth testing in view of its availability throughout the winter. In both cases in which prune juice was given for two weeks there was no

40. Myers, V. C., and Rose, A. R.: *J. A. M. A.* **68**:1022, 1917.

41. Suguira, K., and Benedict, S. R.: *J. Biol. Chem.* **36**:171, 1918.

improvement whatever. It should be added, however, that merely one half ounce a day was given, and that had the dose been considerably larger it may well have exerted some beneficial effect. It is possible that notwithstanding drying and aging a small amount of the antiscorbutic "vitamin" is preserved.

VEGETABLES

The other main class of antiscorbutics consists of vegetables. They vary just as considerably in efficacy as do the various fruits. Those containing the "vitamin" in greatest concentration are the cabbage, the onion, and, according to recent investigations, the swede.⁴² In the first article of this series by Hess and Fish,¹ two instances of mild scurvy were referred to, developing among a group of children in spite of regular daily feeding of carrots, demonstrating that a small daily ration of a vegetable not particularly rich in "vitamin" does not insure protection. In considering vegetables in this connection there are many factors which must be borne in mind. In some experiments on guinea-pigs which are about to be published it was found that old carrots did protect, clearly showing that in regard to their antiscorbutic content vegetables should not be regarded as definite entities. Such results explain, probably, the numerous inconsistencies in the reports of the treatment of scurvy with rations containing vegetables. Another important factor is the duration of the cooking process. It is evident that the older and tougher the vegetable, the longer it must be cooked, so that there is a twofold disadvantage—a food poor in "vitamin" is rendered still poorer by means of the requisite cooking. We have found that the water in which carrots have been cooked contains but a small amount of the antiscorbutic factor. A larger moiety, probably, is washed out in this process than can be ascertained, as some must have been destroyed in the water cooking. Numerous methods have been suggested to conserve the antiscorbutic value of vegetables throughout the winter months. Somewhat over a year ago Chick and Hume²³ recommended the use of germinated pulses for this purpose as suggested by Holst and Froelich.² For this purpose they are kept in the dried state until needed, then soaked in water for about forty-eight hours and allowed to sprout before being used as food. In this way a suitable antiscorbutic may be provided for civil or for army use, one which is not bulky and can be quickly furnished when needed. This suggestion has been successfully carried out recently in the treatment of Serbian soldiers.⁴³

42. Chick, H., and Rhodes, M.: *Lancet*, London **2**: 1918.

43. Wiltshire, H. W.: *Lancet* London **2**:811, 1918.

Some have encouraged the wide use of dehydrated vegetables, claiming that they have all the properties of fresh food. Recently Murlin⁴⁴ has urged an extended use of this product, stating that "by simply soaking in water and boiling in the same water these vegetables are brought back to the condition of fresh vegetables."

In a general review of this subject, published not long ago,¹ we said that such had not been our experience and cited reports taken from the medical histories of our Civil War and other wars, where the dependence of troops on dehydrated vegetables led to the development of scurvy. In view of the increasing importance of this subject, it may be well to give our experience in two cases:

In one instance increasing amounts of dehydrated vegetables were given daily, equivalent to 1, 2, 3 and 6 ounces of fresh carrots for a period of six weeks, without alleviating the scorbutic signs. When the amount of fresh carrots was substituted, all signs disappeared in the course of twelve days.

In another case the same lot of dehydrated carrots was given to the equivalent of 8 ounces a day, but here also there was no therapeutic effect, and when an equal amount of fresh carrots was substituted, the signs disappeared within two weeks.

An attempt to prevent the loss of the "vitamin" by immersing the carrots in a weak solution of citric acid previous to their dehydration was unsuccessful. Our experience with animals coincides with these clinical tests. We do not wish to draw the inference from these results that the dehydrating process, as such, destroys the "vitamin" but merely that in the vegetables employed, which were of excellent appearance and flavor,⁴⁵ the "vitamin" had been almost entirely lost. It is quite possible, indeed probable, that the method of preparing dehydrated vegetables will be perfected so that a product can be furnished which will be comparable in nutritional value to the fresh vegetable. Some unpublished animal experiments have shown that when carrots are dehydrated only a few hours after they are plucked, they retain considerable of their pristine antiscorbutic "vitamin." The problem seems to be one, therefore, that is open to solution. The question of the degree of heating, which is generally regarded as of prime importance, appears to be merely one of several factors. Ideal conditions for furnishing dehydrated vegetables include the use of young vegetables, dehydrating these shortly after they are plucked, keeping them well sealed until they are ready to be eaten, and probably numerous other details which must be carefully observed if deterioration is to be prevented.⁴⁶

44. Murlin, J. R.: Boston M. & S. J. **179**:395, 1918.

45. These carrots were prepared and kindly furnished by the Mrs. Oliver Harriman Food Research Laboratory of this city.

46. It is worth considering in this connection whether the date of the dehydration should not be stated on the package of these foods.

CANNED TOMATOES

For some time we have been looking about for an antiscorbutic which is less expensive than orange juice. In a previous publication it has been shown that a decoction of grated orange peel serves this purpose. This, however, also was not economical, so that for almost a year canned tomatoes have been employed as a substitute in the infant asylum with which we are connected. Tomatoes are not in good repute among food experts in view of the small amount of calories which they contain—only about 100 to the pound—and are regarded with suspicion amounting almost to superstition by mothers and nurses as a food for children. Although poor in calories they

Chart 2.—Cure of scurvy by the addition of canned tomato. In this case, as frequently, the alleviation of symptoms preceded the gain in weight.

are rich in organic acid, stated by some to be mainly citric acid, by others malic acid, and contain also some salicylic acid and traces of benzoic acid.⁴⁷ It may be added, they are rich in "vitamin." Tomatoes undergo a two-fold heating in the course of canning, the second constituting the so-called "processing," during which the temperature is raised to about 230 F. The canned tomatoes were strained through a colander, warmed, and fed through a nursing bottle, one ounce daily being given to an infant a few months of age.⁴⁸ This has been the routine for all infants, and in no instance has there been the least intestinal or nutritional disturbance. From the administrative point of view, this substitute has been valuable in

47. There is no relation whatever between the acidity of canned vegetables and their possible contamination with tin. Experiments carried out to determine this question demonstrated, for example, that a "sample of red kidney beans showing the highest acidity contained the least tin," and that those samples containing the most tin were all relatively low in acidity. (Report of Conn. Agric. Exper. Station Bull. 200, 1917. J. P. Street.)

48. These tests have been controlled by a long series of experiments on animals. Groups of guinea-pigs have been fed on a diet of hay, oats and water, with the addition of various amounts of canned tomato. It was found that 5 c.c. were sufficient invariably to protect a pig from the signs of scurvy. (Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. & Med. **15**:96, 1918.)

saving some hundreds of dollars to the institution. Babies tolerate these tomatoes exceedingly well; in some cases, indeed, the daily amount was increased to 4, 6 and 8 ounces without causing the least untoward symptom. There need be no hesitation in giving a teaspoonful of tomatoes to an infant a few weeks of age, as its acidity is only about one half that of orange juice. They may be boiled, if this is preferred, although it is quite unnecessary; cooking reduces their potency only slightly. All the infants thrived satisfactorily, many of them showing a gain greater than before tomato was substituted for orange juice. This may have been due to the fact that the former contains a considerable amount of water soluble "vitamin," which was demonstrated by means of curative tests on pigeons affected with polyneuritis. During the summer season tomatoes had to be used which had been canned almost a year previously. This aging, however, was noted not to have diminished appreciably their antiscorbutic value, probably on account of the acid reaction and method of preservation. We believe, therefore, that canned tomatoes can safely be recommended as an inexpensive and practical addition to the dietary of the bottle-fed infant.

In this connection it should be added that canned tomatoes form part of the ration of the U. S. Army, in which they can be given "in lieu of an equal quantity of potatoes, not exceeding 20 per cent. of the total issue." We have been unable to ascertain through inquiries from the Surgeon-General's Office the nature of the experience which led to their incorporation in the ration, and whether they were added specifically as an antiscorbutic. They appear for the first time in the revision of the Army Regulations of 1895. The only reference to the antiscorbutic property of canned tomatoes which we have been able to find in the literature is in the excellent treatise by Munson.⁴⁹ That the necessity of including an antiscorbutic in the ration has been recognized only in recent years may be judged by the fact that during our Civil War, and for thirty years thereafter, there was no such provision. It was stated at that time that "a general scorbutic taint pervaded the troops"—a mere euphemism for the widespread existence of subacute or latent scurvy. Even today the ration of the French and of the Italian armies makes no absolute provision in this regard, and the Russians provide merely for a variable quantity of vegetables. When we read that "during the Crimean War the temperature was never very low, and a report of the times suggests that the large number of congelations observed among the soldiers might well be regarded as gangrene owing to a scorbutic tendency exaggerated by the cold,"⁴⁹ it seems quite possible

49. Munson, E. L.: *Military Hygiene*, New York, 1901.

that this factor may have played a rôle in the congelations which occurred in such great numbers among the soldiers in the trenches during the great World War.

In civil life, in framing dietaries for children and for adults, our minds are still focused on insuring a sufficient supply of calories in the food, and we have not yet reacted in practice to the newer knowledge that ample carbohydrates, fats and proteins may constitute a dangerously deficient diet. This same criticism holds true for experimental work on nutrition and on infection, much of which will have to be revised to conform to our broader conceptions of nutrition.

SUMMARY

Numerous reports show that during the late war there was considerable scurvy among the troops of the various armies; least of all along the Western front. The scurvy was mainly of the latent or subacute variety and influenced the character of some of the infectious diseases, and may well have been a factor in the congelations occurring among the soldiers in the trenches. It is evident also that scurvy prevailed among the civilian population to a degree far greater than in peace times.

In infants the question of scurvy centers about the milk supply. An infant requires fully 1 pint of fresh raw milk daily to protect it from this disorder. If the milk is pasteurized, or stale, or heated for a second time, or rendered more sensitive to deterioration by means of an alkali—and particularly if more than one of these influences are operative—more than a pint is needed. The fact that there is an inverse relationship between the amount of milk consumed and the tendency to scurvy shows that we are not dealing with an exogenous toxin and argues in favor of the disorder being primarily a deficiency disease.

Milk does not necessarily lose its antiscorbutic value in the course of drying. If it is dried rapidly even at a temperature of about 240 F. it retains sufficient of the protective factor to have curative value, provided, naturally, that it was fresh at the time of drying. In considering the question of destruction of this "vitamin" by heat or by alkali, the duration of exposure to the detrimental influence is of the greatest importance.

Babies fed on pasteurized milk should receive an antiscorbutic from the time they are a few weeks of age, as there is no reason for allowing the negative balance of "vitamin" to continue for a longer period. A small amount of orange juice will answer the purpose, and is potent for a period after alkalization. Its value does not reside in its laxative properties, nor in its salt content, as "artificial orange juice" has practically no therapeutic effect.

If orange juice is filtered, boiled, and rendered faintly alkaline it may be given intravenously without causing any slightly untoward reaction. In this way a very prompt cure can be accomplished. From a pathogenetic viewpoint a result obtained by this route is of interest as demonstrating that scurvy can be counteracted by a therapy acting quite apart from the alimentary tract.

Diuresis and catharsis do not play an important rôle in the cure of scurvy, as they may be stimulated to a high degree without alleviating the symptoms. This fact argues against regarding this disorder as essentially toxic in nature. It was found also that giving an antiseptic (sodium benzoate) was without effect.

Dehydrated vegetables were ineffective in two instances in which an equivalent amount of fresh vegetable brought about a cure. It is not to be inferred from this result that dehydration necessarily destroys this "vitamin." In this connection too much attention has been paid to the degree of the heating process, and too little to the more important factors—the age of the vegetables, their freshness previous to dehydration, their manner of preservation, etc.

For almost a year strained canned tomatoes have been given, in place of orange juice, to a large number of infants. This substitute has been found a very effective antiscorbutic, and is well borne by babies a few weeks of age. It has the advantage of low cost and availability, and therefore is of particular value for the infants of the poor.